

δ -UZr₂ : Structural stability & thermal expansion coefficient at HP-HT

Balmukund Shukla^{1*}, N R Sanjay Kumar¹, Gurpreet Kaur², N V Chandra Shekar¹, S Kalavathi¹, A K Sinha³, Anuj Upadhyay³, M N Singh³

¹High Pressure Physics Section, Condensed Matter Physics Division,

²Materials Physics Division, Materials Science Group,

Indira Gandhi Centre for Atomic Research, Kalpakkam, HBNI, 603102, Tamil Nadu, India

³Synchrotron Radiation Utilization Division, Raja Ramanna Center for Advanced Technology, Indore 452013, India

*Corresponding author: bshukla@igcar.gov.in, Mob.-9489410203

Abstract

UZr₂ exhibits cubic *bcc* phase at high temperature known as γ -UZr₂ and modified AlB₂ type hexagonal phase at ambient known as δ -UZr₂ (1, 2). HP studies up to 20 GPa on δ -UZr₂ reveals the structure to be stable and bulk modulus is estimated to be 108 GPa. An anomalous increase in the rate of change in *c/a* ratio has been observed beyond 10 GPa. From structural stability computation, this is understood to be due to the strengthening of U-Zr bond, along *a*-axis at lower pressures. The localization of charge density at high pressures indicate decrease in metallization of the material which is in contrast to the usual behavior of the materials at high pressure. *In-situ* HP-HT XRD studies (3) on δ -UZr₂ have been carried out up to 6 GPa and 473 K. The structure is found to be stable and the system exhibits softening as expected. However, *c/a* ratio is found to increase with pressure at high temperatures. Thermal expansion coefficients are estimated and show decreasing trend with pressure.

Keywords - High Pressure, High Temperature, DFT computation, Thermal expansion coefficient

References

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